

DECOMPOSITION ANALYSIS AND GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF CHICKPEA IN VIDARBHA REGION

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Abstract

In present investigation, an attempt was made to study the acreage response and decomposition of chickpea in Vidarbha region. The study was based on secondary data on rainfall, farm harvest price and other data, which were obtained from various Government publications. Nerlovian lagged adjustment model (1958) was used in acreage response analysis based on time series data. The compound growth rates for area, production and productivity under Chickpea was recorded high during period III in all the districts. During period I, the area, production and productivity of chickpea it was registered mostly negative growth rates in all the districts. During period II, the compound growth rate for area, production and productivity under Chickpea has increase in all the districts of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra in the study period. During overall period, Yavatmal district recorded with the highest degree of instability in area i.e. (CV) 83.64 per cent per annum. Similarly in production Buldhana district was recorded with the highest CV i.e. 118.15 per cent per annum and Bhandara+Gondia district was recorded with highest CV in productivity i.e. 46.83 per cent per annum. The highest CII for area and production was found in Gadchiroli district i.e 68.92 and 76.38 per cent per annum, in case of productivity Buldhana district was recorded with the highest degree of instability (CII) i.e. 30.42 per cent per annum. At overall period, the area effect (45.52) was most responsible factor for increasing production in vidarbha region with positive yield and interaction effect i.e., 9.48 and 44.99 per cent respectively.

Key words: Acreage response, decomposition, growth rate, chickpea**Introduction**

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy, contributing significantly to its GDP and providing livelihood to a vast population. In this agrarian landscape, pulses play pivotal role, serving as a primary source of protein and nutrition for millions of people. In India, agriculture and other allied activities contribute significantly to the Gross Domestic product (GDP), accounting for nearly 17.5-18 per cent of the total GDP. It provides employment to around 64 per cent to the total work force. Pulses are a wonderful gift of nature as they nourish mankind with highly nutritive food and keep the soil alive and productive. On account of these virtues, pulse crops remained an integral part of the sustainable agriculture production systems of the semi-arid tropics. India is the largest producer, consumer and importer of pulses in the world, accounting for 33 per cent of the world area and 25 per cent of world production of pulses and 27 per cent of world consumption and 14% importer of pulses in world. In India, during the year 2022-23, pulses were grown on 28 million hectares with the production of 22 -24 million tonnes. Pulses accounts for 20 per cent of area and 7-10 per cent of production to the total food grains of the country. The major pulse producing states in the country are Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh, which together contribute for 75% of the total pulses production in the country. Maharashtra ranks third in pulses production with 21.54 lakh hectares of cultivated area and 15.90 lakh tonnes of production during 2022-23. Chickpea (or) gram is very important rabi pulse crop in the world after peas and beans named *Cicer arietinum* L in the Fabaceae family. In India, major states growing chickpea are Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Maharashtra and Andhra Pradesh etc. Among these states Maharashtra ranks third in acreage under chickpea after Madhya Pradesh and Rajasthan. In Maharashtra it constitute 2830 (000) ha area with the productivity of 20 qtl/ha. The area under chickpea in Maharashtra contributes about 14.50 per cent of total area under chickpea in India, and production of chickpea has share of 14.66 per cent in the total production in chickpea in India (Commissionerate of Agriculture, GOM). In Vidarbha region area under chickpea was 10101 (00 ha) with production of 13180 (00 tonnes) with productivity of 1215 kg/ha.

Material And Methods

The study was undertaken to examine the extent of deviation from planned acreage while making ultimate acreage allocation.

Collection of data

The study was based on secondary data collected from Vidarbha region. The data pertain to the period 1993-94 to 2022-23 and the period was divided into breakup of 10 years with overall as: (a) Period I – 1993-94 to 2002-03, (b) Period II – 2003-04 to 2012-13, (c) Period III – 2013-14 to 2022-23 and (d) Overall period – 1993-94 to 2022-23. Time series secondary data on area, production and productivity of chickpea, data on rainfall, farm harvest price and other relevant data were obtained from many published sources viz., Agricultural Statistical Information of Maharashtra, Epitome of Agriculture and Agricultural situation in India.

Analytical techniques employed for analyzing the data

The present study was based on time series secondary data of chickpea in Vidarbha region.

Growth rate analysis

The compound growth rate of area, production and productivity for chickpea were estimated for three sub periods. The period I was 1993-94 to 2002-03, period II -2003-04 to 2012-13 and period III – 2013-14 to 2022-23. The district wise compound growth rates was estimated to study the growth. It was estimated with the following exponential model:

$$Y = ab^t$$

$$\log Y = \log a + t \log b$$

$$CGR = [\text{Antilog}(\log b) - 1] \times 100$$

Where, CGR=Compound growth rate, Y=Area/Production/Productivity, A= Intercept, b =Regression coefficient or trend value, t=Time period in years

Instability analysis

To measure the instability in area, production and productivity, an index of instability was used as a measure of variability. The coefficient of variation (CV) will be calculated by the formula:

$$CV (\%) = \frac{\text{STANDARD DEVIATION}}{\text{MEAN}} \times 100$$

The simple coefficient of variation (CV) often contains the trend component and thus overestimates the level of instability in time series data characterized by long-term trends. To overcome this problems, we used the instability index (II) given by Coppock's instability index of variation. Coppock's instability index is a close approximation of the

average year to year per cent variation adjusted for trend. The algebraic form of equation is –

$$CII = [(Antilog \sqrt{Vlog} - 1) \times 100]$$

$$\sum \log \left(\frac{X_{t+1}}{X_t} - m \right)^2$$

$$Vlog = \frac{\dots\dots\dots}{N-1}$$

Where, X_t = Area/Production/Productivity in the year 't', N = Number of year, M = Arithmetic mean of difference, V log = Logarithmic variation of the series.

Decomposition of output growth

To measure the relative contribution of area, yield to the total output change for the major crops, Minhas (1964). The decomposition analysis model as given below was used. Sharma (1977) redeveloped the model and several research workers (Kalamkar et al., 2002) used this model and studied growth performance of crops on state. The method states that A_0, P_0 and Y_0 respectively area, production and productivity in base year and A_n, P_n and Y_n are values of the respective variable in n^{th} year item.

$$P_0 = A_0 \times Y_0 \quad \text{and}$$

$$P_n = A_n \times Y_n \quad \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where, A_0 and A_n represents the area and Y_0 and Y_n represents yield in the base year and n^{th} year respectively.

$$P_n - P_0 = \Delta P,$$

$$A_n - A_0 = \Delta A$$

$$Y_n - Y_0 = \Delta Y \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

From equation (1) and (2) we can write

$$P_0 + \Delta P = (A_0 + \Delta A) (Y_0 + \Delta Y)$$

Hence,

Mean of price

Short run Elasticity (SRE) = Regression coefficient of price \times

Mean of area

SRE

Long run elasticity (LRE) =
Coefficient of area adjustment (r)

Where, $r = 1 - (\text{coefficient of lagged area})$.

Observations And Analysis

The results obtained from the present investigation have been presented in the following sub heads:

Growth performance of chickpea

The growth performance of chickpea pertaining to three sub periods and overall period is presented in the Table 1. which reveals that during period I, almost all districts of Vidarbha and Vidarbha region itself showed negative trend except area under chickpea (4.46 per cent per annum) and yield in Bhandara+Gondia (11.00 per cent per annum) respectively.

But during period II, the picture is drastically change. In period II, the area, production and yield of chickpea in Vidarbha region is increased by 7.52, 11.90 and 6.02 per cent per annum respectively. In the case of area, the highest growth rates were observed in Akola+Washim I.e. 10.62 per cent per annum. In the case of production, Yavatmal district

$$P = \frac{A_0 \Delta Y}{\Delta P} \times 100 + \frac{Y_0 \Delta A}{\Delta P} \times 100 + \frac{\Delta Y \Delta A}{\Delta P} \times 100$$

Production = Yield effect +area effect +Interaction effect

Thus, the total change in production can be decomposed into three components viz., yield effect, area effect and the interaction effect area due to change in yield and area.

Acreage response analysis

The model which generally used in supply response analysis based on time series data has been used adaptive expectations or Distributed Lagged model. In the present study the Regression model of the Nerlovian lagged adjustment model (1958) was used. The acreage response means the change in acreage with the unit change in the variables affecting on during the period of study.

$$A_t = a + b_1 A_{t-1} + b_2 FHP_{t-1} + b_3 Y_{t-1} + b_4 W_t + b_5 Y_R + b_6 P_R$$

Where,

a = Area

A_t = Area under crop at time 't' ('00' ha)

A_{t-1} = One year lagged area under the crop ('00' ha)

FHP_{t-1} = Lagged year farm harvest price of the crop (Rs/kg)

Y_{t-1} = One year lagged yield (kg/ha)

W_t = Weather variable as rainfall data per year (mm)

P_R = Price risk (coefficient of variation of last three years)

Y_R = Yield risk (coefficient of variation of last three years)

$b_1 \dots b_6$ = Parameters of multiple linear regression

Short run and long run elasticity

The elasticity's of variables show that the influence of unit change in variable on acreage decisions of crop. In the present study, variable elasticity's were estimated for short run as well as for long run period. Moreover, the short run and long run elasticity were estimated as -

showed highest trend i.e. the production of chickpea was increased by 21.76 per cent per annum. Table 1. also shows that, the area, production and yield of chickpea in Vidarbha region is increased by 6.28, 13.86 and 6.82 per cent per annum over the period of time.

During period III, all districts of Vidarbha region showed increasing trend except Gadchiroli district. In the case of area and production highest growth rate was observed in Buldhana (18.41) and (29.05) per cent per annum respectively. and in the case of yield, the highest growth rate was observed in Nagpur (11.27) per cent per annum.

Table 1. showed that, at overall level almost all district of Vidarbha region and Vidarbha region itself showed positively increasing trend that means the area, production and yield of chickpea in Vidarbha region is significantly increase over the period of time. In Vidarbha region the area, production and yield was increased by 5.67, 8.36 and 3.25 per cent per annum respectively over the period of study.

Table 1. District wise compound growth rates for chickpea

Name of District	Particulars	Period I	Period II	Period III	Over all Period
		CGR	CGR	CGR	CGR
Akola+Washim	Area	4.46*	10.62**	1.28	6.44***
	Production	3.62	8.41	8.39*	8.53***
	Yield	7.56	5.59	7.51**	4.67***
Amravati	Area	-1.53	9.40**	0.18	4.52***

	Production	-2.94	15.73***	5.18*	7.08***
	Yield	-1.46	5.51**	3.40*	2.10***
Bhandara+Gondia	Area	-7.91	9.35**	6.88**	3.78***
	Production	-7.11	13.62*	15.09***	6.62***
	Yield	11.00**	4.57	6.74*	4.94***
Buldhana	Area	-3.75	5.63	18.41***	6.63***
	Production	-7.37	15.36*	29.05***	8.9***
	Yield	-3.66	8.82**	8.94***	2.11***
Chandrapur	Area	0.66	4.47**	6.55***	5.13***
	Production	-2.79	10.34**	17.82***	8.37***
	Yield	-3.49	5.66**	10.62***	3.09***
Gadchiroli	Area	-2.45	-0.62	9.41	4.74***
	Production	0.51	5.07	7.79	5.76***
	Yield	3.07	5.89**	-1.22	1.02*
Nagpur	Area	-0.51	7.77***	1.60	3.59***
	Production	0.29	13.94***	13.13***	7.35***
	Yield	0.81	4.50**	11.27***	3.58***
Wardha	Area	2.39	0.40	7.39**	3.52***
	Production	3.21	4.84	15.88***	7.86**
	Yield	0.81	4.43**	7.84***	4.20***
Yavatmal	Area	2.15	7.30	12.98***	9.06***
	Production	1.67	21.76**	19.90***	12.87***
	Yield	-0.52	8.74***	6.10***	3.34***
Vidarbha region	Area	0.17	7.52**	6.28***	5.67***
	Production	0.43	11.9***	13.86***	8.36***
	Yield	3.59	6.02**	6.82***	3.25***

(Note: ***, ** & * denotes significant at 1%, 5% & 10% level of significance respectively.)

Instability in chickpea

In order to know the instability in area, production and yield of chickpea, the fluctuation measured with the help of coefficient of variation as well as Coppock's index as a coefficient of instability. The results are presented in table 2. and discussed as under for the period with ten years breakage and for over all period also. Fluctuation in area, production and productivity due to the uncontrollable factors like climatic conditions can cause upward bias in coefficient of variation.

The table 2. reveals that during period I, Gadchiroli district recorded with the highest degree of instability in area and production i.e. (CV) 43.48 and 54.41 per cent, (CII) 42.53 and 54.37 per cent per annum. Similarly in productivity Akola+Washim district was recorded with the highest (CV) 42.99 per cent per annum and (CII) 37.28 per cent per annum. In case of CII the lowest degree of instability was recorded for area in Bhandara+Gondia district i.e. 9.38 per cent per annum. On other hand it shows CV in the range of 12.27 to 54.41 per cent per annum and CII in the range of 9.38 to 54.37 per cent per annum which indicate least inconsistent in area, production and productivity of chickpea in all the districts of Vidarbha region and Vidarbha region as a whole.

The instability (CV&CII) in the area, production and productivity was found to be increased in II period as compared to I period in all the districts and Vidarbha region as a whole, (CV&CII) for the yield was less when compared to area and production. During period II, Yavatmal district recorded with the highest degree of instability in area and production i.e. 60.29 & 80.05 (CV) and 5.69 & 62.36 (CII) per cent per annum respectively. Akola+Washim district recorded with the highest degree of instability in productivity i.e. (CV &CII) 37.62 and 34.03 per cent per annum.

During period III, the highest CV for area and production was found in Buldhana district i.e. 52.25 and 77.34 per cent per annum respectively, Nagpur district was recorded with the highest CV in productivity i.e. 35.41 per cent per annum. The highest CII for area and production was found in Gadchiroli district i.e. 40.18 and 49.72 per cent per annum respectively, Bhandara+Gondia district was recorded with the highest degree was instability (CII) for productivity i.e. 28.02 per cent per annum.

During the overall period i.e. 30 years as a whole, the instability (CV & CII) in area, production and productivity was found to be increased in over all period as compared to period III, in all the districts and Vidarbha region as a whole, (CV & CII) for the yield was less when compared to area and production. During overall period, Yavatmal district recorded with the highest degree of instability in area i.e. (CV) 83.64 per cent per annum.

Similarly in production Buldahana district was recorded with the highest CV i.e. 118.15 per cent per annum and Bhandara+Gondia district was recorded with highest CV in productivity i.e. 46.83 per cent per annum. In Nagpur district the lowest CV in area i.e. 35.08 per cent per annum and and for production lowest CV in Amravati district i.e. 65.17 per cent per annum respectively.

In case of Gadchiroli district lowest CV in productivity was observed i.e. 23.68 per cent per annum. The highest CII for area and production was found in Gadchiroli district i.e. 68.92 and 76.38 per cent per annum, in case of productivity Buldhana district was recorded with the highest degree of instability (CII) i.e. 30.42 per cent per annum. Vidarbha region as a whole recorded with the lowest (CII) for area, production

and productivity i.e. 19.44, 29.41 and 18.64 per cent per annum respectively.

Table 2. District wise instability indices in chickpea

Name of District	Particulars	Period I		Period II		Period III		Over all period	
		CV	CII	CV	CII	CV	CII	CV	CII
Akola+Washim	Area	22.86	18.83	33.92	22.97	15.54	15.02	51.31	22.04
	Production	30.46	28.81	43.55	37.95	38.58	31.14	71.91	34.29
	Yield	42.99	37.28	37.62	34.03	29.25	22.14	46.71	30.07
Amravati	Area	19.29	18.72	32.81	22.49	17.71	17.70	43.81	23.65
	Production	27.46	26.08	46.76	29.44	31.41	26.06	65.17	32.98
	Yield	29.35	27.87	23.29	17.44	16.39	13.42	26.64	20.57
Bhandara+Gondia	Area	25.96	9.38	32.38	23.43	29.83	22.86	48.25	34.65
	Production	32.85	26.09	45.55	36.17	52.14	31.14	82.11	53.96
	Yield	42.06	30.89	21.38	18.55	35.38	28.02	46.83	27.29
Buldhana	Area	31.29	29.21	35.28	31.72	52.25	19.81	79.73	44.36
	Production	41.37	35.54	59.29	47.39	77.34	33.98	118.15	74.38
	Yield	26.44	23.59	30.67	20.81	35.25	24.13	35.85	30.42
Chandrapur	Area	19.05	18.93	19.43	14.60	32.97	24.79	48.35	23.51
	Production	25.27	23.82	34.58	21.56	65.92	30.57	89.94	40.75
	Yield	17.52	14.15	24.32	17.58	31.94	12.58	38.03	24.37
Gadchiroli	Area	43.48	42.53	28.91	28.85	45.18	40.18	83.15	68.92
	Production	54.41	54.37	38.68	36.38	52.75	49.72	95.17	76.38
	Yield	24.79	23.48	21.97	15.96	23.68	23.36	23.68	22.17
Nagpur	Area	12.27	12.17	24.57	14.04	16.46	15.51	35.08	19.72
	Production	23.26	23.25	39.04	18.12	45.88	19.26	69.26	29.53
	Yield	20.11	20.01	19.84	15.25	35.41	13.46	41.81	24.52
Wardha	Area	21.31	20.31	20.92	20.89	43.25	32.79	46.73	28.96
	Production	32.62	31.46	35.03	32.28	56.46	24.88	89.42	40.55
	Yield	23.01	22.92	21.25	15.99	27.83	16.37	45.42	24.34
Yavatmal	Area	17.45	16.07	60.29	55.69	37.42	22.65	83.64	35.87
	Production	24.85	24.37	80.05	62.36	49.95	21.01	108.32	47.71
	Yield	26.74	26.69	32.04	19.08	24.22	15.81	36.85	23.52
Vidarbha region	Area	18.18	18.17	29.54	22.12	22.16	9.65	50.53	19.44
	Production	21.75	21.72	40.76	26.35	43.71	18.34	78.21	29.41
	Yield	25.01	23.24	21.62	14.56	21.38	10.12	32.26	18.64

Decomposition of chickpea

The decomposition of chickpea production in area, yield and interaction effect is presented in Table 3. and result demonstrate that per cent contribution of area, yield and their interaction for increasing production of chickpea in Vidarbha region and overall also.

During period I, area effect and yield effect are both the factors which are responsible for increasing chickpea production in Vidarbha region i.e. 95.73 per cent and 3.48 per cent with positive interaction effect i.e. 0.78 per cent. Highest area effect and lowest yield effect were recorded in Gadchiroli district i.e. 103.59 per cent and -5.39 per cent respectively, and the highest interaction effect was observed in Yavatmal district i.e. 57.11 per cent. Bhandara+Gondia district has recorded highest yield effect and lowest area and interaction effect i.e. 732.19 per cent, -323.90 per cent and -308.29 per cent respectively. Overall area effect and yield effect has played a driving force in the differential production of chickpea in Vidarbha region during period I. Domination of both area and yield effect on interaction effect continuous in period II, in Vidarbha region area effect, yield effect and interaction effect were recorded 51.03 per cent, 26.71 per cent and 22.24 per cent respectively. The highest area effect and lowest yield effect were seen in Bhandara+Gondia district i.e. 102.01 per cent and -1.06 per cent respectively, similarly the highest interaction effect was recorded in Yavatmal district i.e. 30.48 per cent. The highest yield effect and lowest area and interaction effect were recorded in Wardha district i.e. 111.11 per cent, -7.52 per cent and -3.58 per cent

respectively. So, it was concluded that in this period area effect and yield effect were responsible for increasing production of chickpea in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra.

During period III, all the districts area effect was positive, also domination of area effect and yield effect on interaction effect continuous in this period, in Vidarbha region positive area effect, yield effect and interaction effect were recorded i.e. 49.32 per cent, 28.35 per cent and 22.32 per cent respectively. The highest area effect and the lowest yield and interaction effect were seen in Gadchiroli district i.e. 479.59 per cent, -253.06 per cent and -126.53 per cent respectively. Similarly the lowest area effect was recorded in Bhandara+Gondia district i.e. 16.60 per cent. The highest yield effect and interaction effect was found in Akola+Washim and Chandrapur district i.e. 64.46 per cent and 34.84 per cent respectively. Bhandara+Gondia district was recorded with the lowest area effect i.e. 16.60 per cent.

During overall period area effect has got domination over the yield effect and interaction effect, except for Bhandara+Gondia district where yield effect was higher than area effect. In Vidarbha region area effect, yield effect and interaction effect recorded were 45.52 per cent, 9.48 per cent and 44.99 per cent respectively.

The highest area effect and lowest yield and interaction effect were recorded in Gadchiroli district i.e. 157.15 per cent, -34.93 per cent and -22.22 per cent respectively. Similarly, the lowest area effect and highest yield effect were seen in Bhandara+Gondia district i.e. 9.63 per cent and 43.10 per cent respectively. The highest interaction effect was

recorded in Akola+Washim district i.e. 56.61 per cent. Thus the result clearly indicate that area effect as well as yield effect both are more responsible factors for production of chickpea in all the districts of

Vidarbha region and Vidarbha region as a whole which was due to evaluation and adoption of improved varieties of chickpea and large area under crop by the farmers of Vidarbha region.

Table 3. per cent contribution area, yield and their interaction for increasing production of chickpea

Name of District	Particulars	Period I	Period II	Period III	Overall period
Akola+ Washim	Area effect	59.84	63.20	30.76	33.99
	yield effect	20.32	14.75	64.46	9.39
	interaction effect	19.83	22.04	4.77	56.61
Amravati	Area effect	-13.34	46.34	86.06	120.33
	yield effect	108.29	24.92	8.95	-4.98
	interaction effect	5.05	28.73	4.98	-15.35
Bhandara+Gondia	Area effect	-323.9	102.01	16.60	9.63
	yield effect	732.19	-1.06	59.31	43.1
	interaction effect	-308.29	-0.94	24.07	47.26
Buldhana	Area effect	11.14	24.91	61.50	88.58
	yield effect	94.00	56.1	12.50	1.45
	interaction effect	-5.15	18.98	25.98	9.95
Chandrapur	Area effect	-16.01	17.89	26.41	38.8
	yield effect	110.49	63.76	38.74	9.82
	interaction effect	5.52	18.34	34.84	51.36
Gadchiroli	Area effect	103.59	41.10	479.59	157.15
	yield effect	-5.39	48.37	-253.06	-34.93
	interaction effect	1.79	10.51	-126.53	-22.22
Nagpur	Area effect	74.93	58.83	17.32	29.52
	yield effect	22.00	21.85	59.87	19.93
	interaction effect	3.06	19.30	22.79	50.54
Wardha	Area effect	95.02	-7.52	48.83	33.89
	yield effect	3.15	111.11	21.73	12.34
	interaction effect	1.81	-3.58	29.43	53.76
Yavatmal	Area effect	-146.04	42.07	55.98	66.3
	yield effect	188.92	27.43	13.59	2.94
	interaction effect	57.11	30.48	30.41	30.74
Vidarbha region	Area effect	95.73	51.03	49.32	45.52
	yield effect	3.48	26.71	28.35	9.48
	interaction effect	0.78	22.24	22.32	44.99

During period III, in all the districts of Vidarbha region yield effect was positive and also yield effect has got domination over the area effect and interaction effect. In whole Vidarbha region area effect, yield effect and interaction effect were 15.65 per cent, 74.04 per cent and 10.30 per cent respectively. The highest area effect was recorded in Wardha district i.e. 73.48 per cent followed by Buldhana, Gadchiroli, Chandrapur, Vidarbha region as a whole, Akola+Washim, Amravati, Nagpur and Bhandara+Gondia district i.e. 71.78, 31.94, 17.78, 15.65, 12.14, 6.67, -1.51 and -30.34 per cent respectively, and the highest yield effect and interaction effect was recorded in Bhandara+Gondia and Gadchiroli district i.e. 137.50 and 22.31 per cent respectively. Similarly the lowest area and interaction effect was recorded in Bhandara+Gondia district i.e. -30.34 and -7.15 per cent respectively. While Buldahana district recorded with the lowest yield effect i.e. 7.49 per cent.

Domination of yield effect on area effect and interaction effect continues in overall period, except for Buldahana and Gadchiroli district where area effect was higher than yield effect. In Vidarbha region area effect, yield effect and interaction effect recorded were 19.66 per cent, 64.49 per cent and 15.83 per cent respectively.

The highest area effect and lowest yield and interaction effect were seen in Buldhana district i.e. 276.75 per cent, -139.80 per cent and -36.95 per cent respectively. Similarly, the lowest area effect and highest yield effect were recorded in Wardha district i.e. -150.77 and 228.05 per cent respectively. Bhandara+Gondia district was recorded with the highest interaction effect i.e. 32.42 per cent. So, the result clearly indicate that in overall period yield effect has played driving force in the differential production of pigeonpea in Vidarbha region.

Acreege response of chickpea

Acreege response functions were fitted to examine the effect of price and non price factors on farmer's decision in allocating the area Chickpea in Vidarbha region. The results obtained are presented and discussed in this section. Table 4. present the district wise estimated acreage response functions of Chickpea grown in most of the part of the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra. Out of two, linear regression model and Cobb-Douglas model, on the basis of number of significant variables, desired signs of estimated regression coefficient and higher R^2 values Cobb-Douglas model was selected with the price and non price variables. With a view of estimating the response of producers in terms of Chickpea area towards price and non price factors the actual

area in the current year was expressed as a log-Cobb-Douglas function of one year lagged area, one year lagged farm harvest prices, one year lagged yield, average annual rainfall, yield risk and price risk. The regression coefficient of these explanatory variables are presented in Table 4. revealed that the lagged area was found to be positively influential factors in the farmer's decision regarding area allocation to Chickpea and found positively significant in all districts of Vidarbha region and Vidarbha region itself except Wardha district which showed negative area allocation.

The coefficient of farm harvest price were less i.e. 0.04, 0.30, 0.49, 0.53, 0.20, 0.40, 0.01, 0.48, 0.45 and 0.39 in Akola+Washim, Amravati, Bhandara+Gondia, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Nagpur, Wardha, Yavatmal and Vidarbha region as a whole respectively. It implied that prices had shown impact in the increase on area of Chickpea in the study period.

One year lagged yield was also included in the function but the coefficient turned out to be very negligible and insignificant in all the districts. Thus implies that one year lagged yield had shown very less impact to area allocation of Chickpea in rest of districts of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra.

The annual rainfall was employed as a proxy for combating the weather influence on the Chickpea hectareage allocation decisions. The coefficient of annual rainfall variable showed positive relationship for

all the districts of Vidarbha region and Vidarbha region itself which showed annual rainfall more influence the area allocation decision of the farmers in all the districts.

The yield risk variable was incorporated in the model gauge the impact of risk over the variation in the acreage under Chickpea. The coefficient of variable had a positive relationship except for Akola+Washim, Bhandara+ Gondia and Nagpur districts which showed a negative relation and statistically insignificant in all the districts of Vidarbha region except Buldhana district showed statistically significant which shows farmers are less risk bearers.

It was also recorded that regression coefficient of price risk variable or factors were insignificant negative relationship in all the districts of Vidarbha region and insignificant positive relationship in Gadchiroli district testified to the farmers risk variation behaviour in Chickpea production.

The value of R² i.e. the coefficient of multiple determinations ranged from 0.65 to 0.93 for all the districts of Vidarbha region. It was 0.93, 0.89, 0.74, 0.85, 0.80, 0.72, 0.88, 0.65 and 0.83 found in Akola+Washim, Amravati, Bhandara+Gondia, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Nagpur, Wardha and Yavatmal districts respectively, which indicates that variables included in model explained most of the variations in area under Chickpea in the study period.

Table 4. Coefficients for acreage response function of chickpea

Coefficients	Particulars	One year lagged area	One year lagged farm harvest prices	One year lagged yield	Annual rainfall	Yield risk	Price risk	Coefficient of determination
	Intercepts	A _{t-1}	FHP _{t-1}	Y _{t-1}	W _t	Y _r	P _r	R ²
Akola+Washim	-3.66	0.85***	0.04	0.02	1.39***	-0.12	-0.01	0.93
Amravati	-3.08	0.57***	0.30***	0.06	1.00***	0.09	-0.01	0.89
Bhandara+Gondia	-0.64	0.59***	0.49***	-0.24	0.22	-0.09	-0.02	0.74
Buldhana	-4.01	0.49***	0.53***	0.35	0.79*	0.32***	-0.06	0.85
Chandrapur	-1.44	0.65***	0.20	0.15	0.36	0.07	-0.04	0.80
Gadchiroli	-3.30	0.60***	0.40**	-0.07	0.78	0.23	0.06	0.72
Nagpur	-1.20	0.92***	0.01	0.04	0.42*	-0.02	-0.03	0.88
Wardha	-1.64	-0.04	0.48***	0.10	0.79*	0.01	-0.06	0.65
Yavatmal	-3.38	0.70***	0.45*	-0.06	0.92	0.10	-0.01	0.83
Vidarbha region	-2.11	0.55***	0.39***	-0.09	0.93***	0.01	-0.01	0.91

Short run and long run elasticity of chickpea

The variation in the magnitude of short run and long run price elasticity factors between different districts of Vidarbha region were evident from Table 5. The short run and long run price elasticities of Chickpea showed positive price responsiveness of farmers in all the districts of Vidarbha and region Vidarbha region as a whole.

Table 5. District wise Price Elasticity of chickpea in Vidarbha region

Sr. No.	Name of Districts	SRE	LRE
1	Akola+Washim	0.09	0.63
2	Amravati	0.96	2.31
3	Bhandara+Gondia	8.64	21.34
4	Buldhana	1.68	3.32
5	Chandrapur	1.83	5.27
6	Gadchiroli	15.54	38.95
7	Nagpur	7.64	99.62
8	Wardha	3.78	3.62
9	Yavatmal	1.94	6.58
10	Vidarbha region	0.21	0.48

The short run price elasticities are 0.09, 0.96, 8.64, 1.68, 1.83, 15.54, 7.64, 3.78 and 1.94 for Akola+Washim, Amravati, Bhandara+Gondia, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Nagpur, Wardha and Yavatmal districts respectively. The highest short run price elasticity was found in Gadchiroli district i.e. 15.54 and lowest short run price elasticity was found in the Akola+Washim district i.e. 0.09.

The long run elasticity for Akola+Washim, Amravati, Bhandara+Gondia, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Nagpur, Wardha and Yavatmal districts area 0.63, 2.31, 21.34, 3.32, 5.27, 38.95, 99.62, 3.62 and 6.58 respectively. It was also recorded from the table that long run price elasticities are comparatively higher than the short run price elasticities in Akola+Washim, Amravati, Bhandara+Gondia, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Nagpur and Yavatmal districts and Vidarbha region as a whole indicated that the farmers were relatively market oriented in their decisions in the long run than in the short run. Whereas, in Wardha district short run price elasticities are slightly higher than the long run price elasticity indicating that farmers were relatively market oriented in their decisions in the short run rather than long run in response to the Chickpea in the Vidarbha region of the Maharashtra.

The long run elasticity for Akola+Washim, Amravati, Bhandara+Gondia, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Nagpur, Wardha and Yavatmal districts area 0.63, 2.31, 21.34, 3.32, 5.27, 38.95, 99.62, 3.62 and 6.58 respectively. It was also recorded from the table that long run price elasticities are comparatively higher than the short run price elasticities in Akola+Washim, Amravati, Bhandara+Gondia, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli, Nagpur and Yavatmal districts and Vidarbha region as a whole indicated that the farmers were relatively market oriented in their decisions in the long run than in the short run. Whereas, in Wardha district short run price elasticities are slightly higher than the long run price elasticity indicating that farmers were relatively market oriented in their decisions in the short run rather than long run in response to the Chickpea in the Vidarbha region of the Maharashtra.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the compound growth rates for area, production and productivity under chickpea was recorded high during period III in all the districts. During period I, the area, production and productivity of chickpea registered mostly negative growth rates in all the districts. During period II, the compound growth rate for area, production and productivity under chickpea has increase in all the districts of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra in the study period. Percent contribution of yield effect was most responsible factor for chickpea in the initial period but later area effect was more pronounced. Current year acreage was less influenced by farm harvest prices and not by one year lagged yield of chickpea in all the districts. The long run price elasticities were greater than short run elasticities in chickpea indicating that farmers were relatively market oriented in their decisions.

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